

Influence of Brij-35 micelles on the oxidation of glycine by hexacyanoferrate(III) in aqueous alkaline medium

Anjali Goel* and Richa Tyagi

Department of Chemistry, Kanya Gurukul Mahavidyalaya, Gurukul Kangri University, Haridwar-249 407, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : goelanjali@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 11 August 2009, revised 26 April 2010, accepted 17 May 2010

Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of glycine by hexacyanoferrate(III) in presence of non-ionic surfactant Brij-35 has been studied under pseudo-first order conditions in alkaline medium. It has been found that increase in [Brij-35] causes increase in reaction rate indicating that the reaction is enhanced by non-ionic micelles. The reaction is first order in [hexacyanoferrate(III)], [glycine] and [NaOH]. Glyoxalic acid is identified as the main product of oxidation.

Keywords : Micelles, glycine, hexacyanoferrate(III), Brij-35.

Introduction

The rate of a chemical reaction may be modified by the presence of micellar aggregation in the system under reaction. Physico-chemical investigations of surfactants in aqueous or mixed solvents provide a lot of information about their microscopic structure in solutions¹⁻⁷. Surfactant aggregates (micelles) in solution provide a unique micro-environment for solubilization and an enzyme like catalytic effect for several chemical reactions⁸⁻¹⁶. The structure of both micelles and enzymes are similar in that they have hydrophobic cores with polar groups on their surfaces. The effect of surfactants in the bromination¹⁷, hydrolysis¹⁸ and complexation¹⁹ has been studied by several workers²⁰⁻²³ from time to time but the use of surfactants in the oxidation of amino acids by hexacyanoferrate(III) (abbreviated as HCF(III)) is still unknown. Thus in the present study the effect of surfactant on the oxidation of glycine by hexacyanoferrate(III) has been carried out.

Results and discussion

The kinetic study of the oxidation of glycine by HCF(III) in aqueous alkaline medium was carried out under set of condition both in the presence and absence of non-ionic surfactant. The aim of the work was to observe the behaviour of surfactants in the redox chemistry of amino acids and compare the results with those in aqueous medium under similar reaction condition.

(i) Kinetics in absence of surfactant :

The reaction is carried out at various fixed [oxidant] keeping other variables viz. [glycine], [OH⁻], ionic strength and temperature constant. The increase in rate over a concentration range of HCF(III) (Fig. 1) is in agreement with a first order dependence on [HCF(III)]. The rate law, is therefore, given as

$$\frac{-d[\text{HCF(III)}]}{dt} = v = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{HCF(III)}]$$

Fig. 1. Dependence of rate on [HCF(III)] for the oxidation of glycine by HCF(III) in the absence and presence of [Brij-35] at 30 °C : [Glycine] = 3.00 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³, [Brij-35] = 4.5 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1 °C.

In the presence of fixed [oxidant] = 3×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ and [OH⁻] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³ at 30 °C, the rate of oxidation increased linearly with the increase of [glycine] (Fig. 2). The plot of log k_{obs} vs [glycine] was linear with slope indicating first order dependence on [glycine].

Fig. 2. Dependence of rate on [glycine] for the oxidation of glycine by HCF(III) in the absence and presence of [Brij-35] at 30 °C : [HCF(III)] = 3.00×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³, [Brij-35] = 4.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.5$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1 °C.

The oxidation rate increases linearly with increase of [OH⁻] under the condition [glycine] = 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ and [oxidant] = 3×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ at 30 °C (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Dependence of rate on [NaOH] for the oxidation of glycine by HCF(III) in the absence and presence of [Brij-35] at 30 °C : [Glycine] = 3.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [HCF(III)] = 3.00×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [OH⁻] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³, [Brij-35] = 4.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 0.5$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1 °C.

The reaction was carried out at different temperatures in the range of 35 to 50 °C. Different activation parameters were evaluated using both Arrhenius and Eyring equations (Table 1).

Mechanism of reaction :

It is well known that amino acids exist as zwitterions in aqueous solution²⁴. In alkaline solution, the zwitterion is converted into anion, RCH(NH₂)CO₂⁻ which is the reactive species under the present experimental conditions. Since HCF(III) is a one electron oxidant, it can be assumed that the reaction proceeds through the imino acid formation which underwent hydrolysis to give the keto-acid and ammonia.

(ii) Kinetics in presence of surfactants :

The critical micelle concentration was determined from the plot of conductivity vs [Brij-35]. The break in the curve was taken as cmc (Fig. 4). The value was found 4.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ at temperature 30°C and ionic strength 0.5 mol dm⁻³. cmc does not changes with [Glycine],

Fig. 4

[HCF(III)], [OH⁻] and ionic strength of the solution. But it shows small decreases with the increase of temperature. The increase in temperature causes dehydration of the polyoxyethylene chain resulting in the decrease of cross sectional area occupied by hydrophobic group at micelle solution interphase. It also appears to produce a sharp increase in the asymmetry of micelle.

To study the effect of [Brij-35] concentration on rate of oxidation, the reaction was studied at different concentrations of the surfactant. The plot of rate vs [surfactant] depicts a curve with a maximum at [Brij-35] of $4.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Effect of [Brij-35] on reaction rate.

The rate of reaction increases with the increase of [Brij-35] and then decreases with the increase of Brij-35 concentration. This behaviour is in agreement with the micellar catalysis of organic molecular type. It may be due to the Stern layer of the micelle which increases rapidly with increasing concentration of Brij-35 and substrate relatively²⁴.

It has been established that surfactant may change the mechanism of a reaction. Therefore, to confirm the mechanism vis-à-vis micelle-free medium, the reaction rate were determined over a range of [glycine], [HCF(III)], [OH⁻] and temperature at fixed [Brij-35] (Figs. 1-3). The results show that the kinetics follow the first order in substrate, oxidant and hydroxide concentration. These observations undoubtedly establish that the mechanism of oxidation of glycine by [HCF(III)] in the presence of Brij-35 remains the same as in the absence of surfactants.

The reaction rate was not influenced by the addition of chemically neutral salts like potassium chloride. Hence the ionic behaviour of slow steps in the reaction mechanism is ruled out.

The activation parameters obtained in the aqueous as well as in the Brij-35 media (Table 1) show that the magnitude of ΔS^* is not significantly affected, indicating that

Table 1. The activation parameters E_a , ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* for the oxidation of glycine ($3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) by HCF(III) ($3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in NaOH (0.4 mol dm^{-3}) and [Brij-35] = $4.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Parameters (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Value	
	With surfactant	Without surfactant
E_a (kcal mol ⁻¹)	15.1	17.8
ΔH^* (kcal mol ⁻¹)	14.5	17.1
ΔS^* (e.u.)	-24.9	-44.6
ΔG^* (kcal mol ⁻¹)	22.1	31.2

the same mechanism is being followed in aqueous as well as in micellar media. A meaningful mechanistic explanation of the ΔH^* and ΔS^* is not possible because the k_{obs} does not represent a single elementary kinetic step. It is a complex function of adsorption, binding and ionization constants.

Theoretical and quantitative treatment of micellar effect :

The rate of acceleration in micellar solutions arises from different rate of the substrate in the micellar phase and the bulk solution and the distribution of the substrate between these two phases. This rate acceleration may be due to electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions between the substrate and the surfactant aggregate.

The present kinetic results have been explained on the basis of Piskiewicz model¹⁴. According to this model, substrate (S) and surfactant aggregates (Dn) combine to form the catalytic complex (DnS) which then reacts to form the product.

The observed rate constant k_{obs} can be expressed as a function of the surfactant concentration $[D]$ by eq. (1) which on rearrangement gives eq. (2).

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_m [D]^n + k_w K_D}{K_D + [D]^n} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of surfactant molecules, D , DnS is the catalytic micelle. K_D is the dissociation constant of the micelle and k_m and k_w are rate constant of the micellar and aqueous phase respectively. The rate expression (1) may be written as

$$\log \left[\frac{k_{obs} - k_w}{k_m - k_{obs}} \right] = n \log [D] - \log K_D \quad (2)$$

According to eq. (2), a linear relationship obtained between $\log \left[\frac{k_{obs} - k_w}{k_m - k_{obs}} \right]$ and $\log [D]$ justifies the applicability of this model (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6

The slope ' n ' is considered as the index of cooperativity. The value of n is greater than 1 referring to positive cooperativity. This implies that the interaction of the first molecule with micelles stimulates the interaction of additional substrate molecules. Also, at $\log \left[\frac{k_{obs} - k_w}{k_m - k_{obs}} \right] = 0$, catalysis by detergent shows one-half of its maximum effect on rate constant. For convenience the value of $\log [D]$ at this point is designated as

$\log [D]_{50}$, and it is equal to $(\log K_D)/n$. The $\log [D]_{50}$ from the above Fig. 6 is $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-1}$ which is in good agreement with observed value ($2.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) (Fig. 5).

This analysis was applied only to the region of surfactant concentration in which the initial sigmoid dependence of k_{obs} on surfactant concentration was seen. It did not include the region at very high surfactant concentration where k_{obs} often decreases in bimolecular reactions. Slopes of the double log plots, n , were calculated by least-square analysis.

Probabilistic reaction site : As far as the role of non-ionic micelles of Brij-35 is concerned, hydrogen bonding between the non-ionic micelles and the reactant play an important role. Due to this, both the reactants can be concentrated into the small volume of Brij-35 micelles. HCF(III) and glycine both possess no hydrophobic character. There may occur hydrogen bonding between the -OH group of glycine and -OH group of the non-ionic Brij-35. Possibility of the hydrogen bonding between

HCF(III) and hydrophilic part of the Brij-35 micelles can not be ruled out either. Formation of an ester-like species between oxidant and organic reductants is a characteristic feature of the mechanism of these reaction. Therefore, the associated oxidant and glycine with Brij-35 micelles (through hydrogen bonding) seem responsible of facilitating formation of an ester. This might be the main role of Brij-35 micelles towards catalysis.

Experimental

The surfactant Brij-35 (E. Merck) was used as received. Hexacyanoferrate(III) (oxidant), KCl were used after recrystallization. Glycine used was of AR grade. The water used as solvent was previously subjected to deionization followed by distillation (specific conductance $1-2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$).

The kinetic experiments were carried out by mixing the measured quantity of glycine solution (pre-equilibrated at the same temperature) with solution of HCF(III), Brij-35 (surfactant), sodium hydroxide and potassium chloride kept at the same temperature. The concentration of HCF(III) was not kept more than $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. All experiments were carried out in thermostatic water bath at constant temperature $30 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and ionic strength 0.5 mol dm^{-3} . Potassium chloride was used to keep the ionic strength constant.

The progress of the reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} 420 nm. Plane mirror method was used for evaluation of initial rates $[(dA/dt)_i]$. Pseudo-first order rate constant ($k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$) were computed from the slopes of log (absorbance) vs time plots ($r \geq 0.99$). The second order rate constant ($k_{11} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and initial rates ($\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) were evaluated from the relation: $k_{11} = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{glycine}]$ and $v = k_{\text{obs}} \times [\text{glycine}]$.

The reaction mixture containing excess of [oxidant] was allowed to react with glycine solution at room temperature for 24 h. The unreacted HCF(III) was estimated by ceric(IV) sulphate solution. The estimated value shows that one mole of glycine consumed two mole of HCF(III) giving glyoxalic acid as the main oxidation product.

The product was confirmed by spot test and TLC using the solvent of ethanol and ammonia. Ferric chloride was used as locating agent.

Conclusion :

On the basis of the above study, it can be concluded that presence of Brij-35 surfactant increase the rate of the proposed reaction. Piszkwicz model confirms that micellar-catalysed reaction follows same mechanism in absence and presence of Brij-35.

References

1. M. J. Rosen, A. W. Cohen, M. Dahanayake and X. Y. Hua, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, **86**, 541.
2. K. Satyender Yadav, Ashok Kumar and O. P. Yadav, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 532.
3. E. J. Fendler, S. A. Chang, H. J. Fendler and R. T. Medary, "Reaction Kinetics in Micelles", ed. E. H. Cordes. Plenum Publishing Co., New York, 1973, 127.
4. Z. Khan, Kabir-ud-Din and Mohd. Sajid Ali, *Colloid Polym. Sci.*, 2007, **285**, 752.
5. A. V. Kireyko, I. A. Veselova and T. N. Shekhovtsova, *Russian Journal of Bioorganic Chemistry*, 2006, **32**, 77.
6. Ghanat K. Joshi, Y. R. Katre and Ajaya K. Singh, *Journal of Surfactants and Detergents*, 2006, **9**, 235.
7. A. Yoshino, H. Okabayashi, T. Vchida, T. Ogasawara and T. Yoshida, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 8418.
8. G. P. Panigrahi and S. K. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 956.
9. J. Panda and G. P. Panigrahi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 1636.
10. K. Anand, O. P. Yadav and P. P. Singh, *Colloids & Surfaces*, 1991, **55**, 345.
11. M. Chiarni and C. A. Bunton, *Colloid Surf. (A)*, 2004, **245**, 177.
12. C. A. Bunton, E. J. Fendler and J. H. Fendler, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1221.
13. E. F. Duynstee and E. Grunwald, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, **21**, 2401.
14. D. Piszkwicz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 1550.
15. Kabir-ud-Din, J. K. Salem and S. Kumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1019.
16. Z. Khan, S. I. Ali, Md. Z. A. Rafique and Kabir-ud-Din, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 579.
17. A. K. Panigrahi, S. Mishra, M. Patra and B. K. Sinha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 398.
18. K. K. Ghosh and Santhosh Kumar Sar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 581.
19. T. K. Joy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 435.
20. K. K. Kishore, A. Kalyan Kumar, N. Annapurna and P. Vani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 377.
21. G. P. Panigrahi and R. Swain, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1191.
22. Kabir-ud-Din, U. Salma and Z. Khan, *J. Surf. Sci. Technol.*, 2003, **36**, 101.
23. Kabir-ud-Din, A. M. A. Morshed and Z. Khan, *J. Carbohydr. Chem.*, 2003, **22**, 843.
24. D. Laloo and M. K. Mahanti, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 311.
25. V. Nagar, S. K. Solanki and V. R. Shastry, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 959.

